

Anisotropic Mechanical Properties of Advanced High Performance Fibers Obtained by a Single Fiber Testing System

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ABSTRACT : The detail of the anisotropic mechanical properties and strength of high performance fibers, especially Aramid fibers is presented. This investigation of the fiber properties was carried out by using the system of single fiber measurement which has been developed recently. The elastic modulus in longitudinal extension, compression, transverse compression and torsion are presented. The nonlinear mechanical behaviors, viscoelasticity and strength in the corresponding deformations are also presented and discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

High performance fibers made of polymers are now widely used as a reinforcement material of composites. Their strength supports the strength of the composite and, therefore, the properties of these fibers must be carefully considered in the design of composites. These fibers have strong anisotropy of mechanical properties including strength. This is caused by the strong orientation of polymer molecular chains along the fiber axis. The detail of the anisotropy in the mechanical properties of the fibers, however, have not been explained from the stand point of fiber measurement, only estimated by composite properties.

Recently, a direct measurement system of the mechanical properties of single fibers has been developed,¹⁾ and has clarified the anisotropic properties without disturbances coming from fiber bundle and composite effect. The result is presented here concentrating on the properties of Aramid fibers.

2. THE MEASUREMENT SYSTEM

The system consists of four main testers, and three of additional testers for torsion fatigue²⁾ and creep testers³⁾. The fiber properties measured by these testers are as follows.

Table 1. The single fiber testers

1. Longitudinal extension	Precise tensile tester with low mechanical noise for single fibers
2. Longitudinal compression	Compression testing using micro composite methods(not single fibers)
3. Transverse compression	Transverse compression of single fibers
4. Torsion	Precise torsion testing of single fibers using a micro torque detector
5. Poisson's ratio ν_{LT}	Micro-diameter detecting with longitudinal extension

The anisotropic property of the fiber-symmetric body is expressed by five parameters if the body is elastic as shown in Fig.1. These parameters are completely measurable by the above system. In addition, the nonlinear behavior and strength in the deformations corresponding to these parameters may also be measured by this system.

Fig.1 Anisotropic elastic parameters of fiber symmetric body

Fig.2 Transverse compression of single fiber

In Fig.2, the principle of the transverse compression is shown. The diametrical change is around $0.1 \mu\text{m} \sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ and recorded as a function of applied compression force. The transverse modulus may be derived from this curve³⁾.

Fig.3 The micro-composite specimen for the measurement of longitudinal compression property of fiber

Fig.4 Cross-section of the micro-composite

The longitudinal compression of fiber is measured by using the micro composite which is a composite of unidirectional fibers having high fiber content of around 80%.⁴⁾ This high value of the fiber content was realized by means of the micro composite which is a rod-like shape 4 mm in length and 0.5~1 mm in diameter. The shape of the composite and its cross section are shown in Figs 3 and 4 respectively. The high compactness prevents the buckling of fibers under axial compression.

This was proved by the test of the compression of glass fibers which have the same property of longitudinal compression and extension and where these two s-s curves are well connected and form a straight line as seen in Fig. 6. In spite of this, these two curves were measured by respective different testers and principles.

3. THE PROPERTY OF ARAMID FIBERS

The elastic constants of Aramid fibers, Kevlar 29 and 49(@Du Pont Co.) are shown in Table 2. This data was obtained in the linear region of mechanical properties. The Poisson's ratio ν_{LT} was also confirmed by the measurement of the Poisson's ratio of a composite plate having high volume fraction of fiber(around 80%).

Table 2. Elastic parameters of Aramid fibers measured by the single-fiber testing system

	Kevlar 49	Kevlar29
Symbol	DK49	DK29
Fiber Dia.(mm)	13.8	13.8
E_L (GPa)		
Initial region	113.4	79.8
Breaking region	129.6	98.4
E_T (GPa)	2.49	2.59
G_{LT} (GPa)	2.01	2.17
ν_{LT}	0.62	0.63
ν_{TT}	0.31	0.43

The full properties of these fibers including the nonlinear region are shown in Fig. 5~7. The longitudinal extension and compression properties measured by the extension of single fiber and the compression of the micro composite specimen respectively are connected and shown in Fig. 5. The compression properties have a stress yielding at a much lower stress level compared with tensile strength. As a reference, the properties of E-glass fiber are shown in Fig.6. The curve is a straight line through the extension and compression deformations. This result also proves the accuracy of the testing method of longitudinal compression.

Fig.5 Longitudinal compression property of Kevlar 49

Fig.6 Longitudinal compression property of E-glass fiber

Fig.7 shows the transverse properties of these Kevlar fibers under a constant rate of compression⁵). The fiber property in this direction also shows stress yielding. The recovery of deformation after the yielding stress shows a large hysteresis. The property is almost plasticity in this deformation. The yielding stress is also much lower than the braking stress in the longitudinal tensile deformation.

Fig.7 Transverse compression property of Kevlar single fivers. Tensile modulus of these fibers are the 149>49>29.

In the torsion deformation, the fiber is subjected by shear deformation along the fiber axis. The torsion property, therefore, is associated with the inter-molecular chains force, or inter fibrils forces, which are much weaker than the force to extend the primary bonds of the chain molecules. The torsion property under a constant rate of twisting is shown in Fig.8. The torque yielding can also be observed in this deformation property.

Fig.8 Torsional property of Kevlar 49

4. VISCOELASTICITY AND FATIGUE DURABILITY

Polymers are viscoelastic materials in general. Aramid fibers are also viscoelastic body. The creep measurements of these fibers were carried out in the deformations of longitudinal extension, transverse compression and torsion for Kevlar® 29. These results show that:

1. The creep deformations in the transverse and shear deformations are much larger than that of the longitudinal deformation in absolute amount, however, the creep deformation in the longitudinal deformation exists, its effect on the composite property may not be neglected.

2. The source of the viscoelasticity seems to be in the amorphous region inside fiber. A common creep function appears in the longitudinal, transverse and shear properties with the proportions as follows. The compliance in the transverse direction is written by,

$$J_T(t) = J_{0T}(1 + \phi(t)) \quad (1)$$

Then, the compliance in the longitudinal direction is

$$J_L(t) = J_{0L}(1 + c \phi(t)), \quad c=0.062 \quad (2)$$

3. The creep in the torsion is almost same as that in the transverse direction.

In the longitudinal direction, the effect of creep function $\phi(t)$ on its compliance is about 6.2% of that in the transverse direction. Even though this is much smaller than that of the transverse direction, the effect is not negligible. The $\phi(t)$ becomes about 30% of the elastic component J_{ET} after loading. This must be considered in the design of composites. Fig.9 shows the creep compliance $J_V(t)$ for the three directions⁶⁾, where $J_V(t)$ is defined as follows.

$$J(t) = J_0 + J_V(t) \quad (3)$$

Fig.9 Master curves of creep compliance of Kevlar 29 in three directions, referred to 35°C

The failure of the high performance fibers during their use in composites or fibrous materials occurs as follows. Repeated loading or deformations of fiber induces the failure of the weakest part in fiber, that is, inter-molecular bonding, inter-fibril bonding etc, and this failure then induces fibrication of fibers. This fibril separation remarkably reduces the longitudinal strength of the fiber. In order to predict the failure in the weakest part of fiber, the torsion fatigue test is important. Fig. 10 shows the reduction of the shear modulus^{7),8)} during the repeated torsion cycles by using a master curve referred to a strain amplitude of 0.034. This process is well normalized by the principle of Strain amplitude/ Fatigue cycles superposition which is similar to Temperature/Time superposition in the viscoelasticity of amorphous polymers.

Fig.10 Torsion fatigue of Kevlar 49 single fiber, referred to skin strain $\gamma_m = 0.037$

5. CONCLUSION

The high performance fibers have a strong anisotropy in their mechanical behavior. In the longitudinal direction, the modulus and strength is high in extension, however, weak in compression. In the transverse and torsion deformations, the modulus becomes much smaller than it does in extension, about 1/30 ~1/50 for Aramid fibers. Stress yielding also appears in these deformations. The fiber property in these deformations is plasticity. The fibers have viscoelasticity in the longitudinal, transverse and torsion deformation. The source of the viscoelasticity may be in the amorphous part and it appears in these three deformations. The damage of the fibers during use in the composites or fibrous materials occurs by the failure of fiber in the weakness in the inter-molecules, or inter-fibril bonding of the fibers.

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